

Design of a Composite Draw Bridge

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ABSTRACT

The Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO, by assignment of the Dutch Ministry of Transport, Public Works and Water Management (Ministry of Transport) has designed a composite draw bridge. In the design a conventional steel upper lifting structure has been combined with a full composite bridge deck. The bridge is a class 450 bridge (up to 150kN axle load) with a span of 10 m and a width of 3m, for an intensively used connection in Den Dungen the Netherlands. Aim of the development is to design a safe highly loaded composite structure that can be manufactured cost effectively by means of a resin infusion process. Motivation for the Ministry of Transport is to achieve reduced maintenance costs and to learn about the possibilities of composite materials in civil structures. This paper addresses the design process of the bridge, for which an integrated approach was used and a fail safe design philosophy. It also describes the resulting structure and explains the motivations for the structural solutions chosen.

Figure 1: draw bridge Den Dungen

1 Introduction

Fibre reinforced plastics are increasingly popular for use in civil structures such as bridge structures. In the past years several composite bridges have been realised: pedestrian bridges, but also traffic bridges such as in the USA, Australia and the United Kingdom. From these examples it is seen that each situation and location has its own motivation for using composites. Low weight in combination with high strength, means lower transportation costs and allows for a quicker placement of the bridge using lighter equipment. Quicker placement means a much shorter closing of the roads and reduces the economic impact. Especially for urban area and railway closings, the latter costs are substantial, involving tens or even hundreds of thousands Euros per day.

In an outback situation maintenance is the problem to be solved and in countries with harsh winters, de-icing salts cause major damage to concrete and steel bridges [1]. When comparing to steel, which is commonly used in movable bridges such as this type of draw bridge, the greatly improved durability and low maintenance of composite materials are a great advantage.

Most of the presently realised composite bridge projects are structures based on pultruded elements. This is at present without doubt the most cost effective manufacturing method for realising composite profiles, however with this method usually a large percentage of lower grade materials such as random mat, is used. This is not desired for movable bridges, because the points of load introduction require high strength and local reinforcements have to be applied.

This study aims on realising a structure made with a low cost resin infusion technique, such as vacuum infusion or film infusion, because with this technique high quality stitched fabric can be used and variations in material lay up can be integrated in the structure. For this project only a single product is considered, the fact that with this manufacturing method large structures can be made with simple tooling is a great advantage.

2 Bridge configuration, loads and criteria

The draw bridge considered in this study has a span of 10m and a width of 3m (see figure 2).

Figure 2: draw bridge configuration

The bridge is supported on four points, two points at each end, and by the two hanging rods that carry the balance weights. At the other end a locking device prevents the deck from jumping up when traffic leaves the bridge. A single hydraulic cylinder opens and closes the bridge, which means that this force is applied asymmetrically.

The small width is characteristic for this bridge: there is only one lane, over which the traffic in turn runs in each direction. The bridge is next to an intersection, and the traffic will have a maximum speed of 50 km/h when crossing the bridge.

The stiffness criteria is $L/300$, and is lower than the more common value of $L/600$ or $L/800$. In this case it is acceptable because a person can never be walking on the bridge when a truck passes. The vertical acceleration of the person caused by the deflection of the bridge is only due to his own weight and will be far below 0.5 m/s^2 , the criteria of comfort.

It is a class 450 bridge, with a maximum vehicle load of 450kN equally divided over three axles. A load factor of 1.5 has to be applied, as well as a dynamic factor of 1.4. The design life of the bridge is 50 years.

The loads are specified by the Ministry and derived from the Dutch Standards NEN 6788 [2] and NEN 6786 [3] and the preliminary traffic loads for bridges of the preliminary Eurocode [4].

Load cases considered are:

- Dead weight and balance weight loads
- Traffic loads (wheel pressures and distributed loads for ultimate and normal condition and fatigue loads [4])
- Friction loads
- Wind pressure loads (open condition)
- Temperature load
- Loads on the cylinder, points of rotation and locking device
- Impact
- Fire

A general strength criterion was used, in which the maximum allowable strain for all directions is 1.2 %. This can be applied under the condition of a minimum of 15% fibres in every direction

(0°, 90°, +45°, -45°) [5]. Safety factors are applied on loads and on material properties, to account for manufacturing defects, creep, fatigue and thermal and environmental effects, as prescribed in [5] and [6].

3 Structural Concepts and preliminary design

It is the aim of the development to achieve a safe structure that can be manufactured cost effectively by means of a resin infusion process. The design is driven by the weight target (9500kg) and costs, mainly determined by the cost for labour for manufacturing and assembly. The spanning structure can be sandwich or built up out of profiles. In figure 3 a few examples of structural concepts are shown.

Figure 3: examples of structural concepts

A first selection was made based on the number of elements (labour cost for manufacturing and assembly), structural efficiency (material cost) and fail safety of the structure.

The second concept shown in figure 3 was rejected for its failure mode: when the coupling layer on top of the boxes fails, there is a high risk on desintegration of the structure. The first concept in figure 3 was not efficient enough: the transverse webs do not contribute to the spanwise stiffness. The profile of the structural beam of Concept V is much more complex to produce with infusion technology than those of concept III and IV and was therefore rejected.

The most important decision to be taken in this stage was to use an integrated deck (concept IV), or to apply a separate road deck (concept III).

Figure 4: integrated deck and a double layer structure with a separate road deck.

Without a separate deck, damage on the road surface leads to damage on the principal structure, whereas when a separate road deck is applied the deck profiles function as a safety buffer. In case of damage only the road deck profiles need to be replaced

For a concept without separate deck it is necessary to take measures to protect the structure against fire and this must be checked by a fire test. Impact tests must be performed to verify the residual structural performance of the structure. For fire the criterion is that structural integrity must be maintained, sufficient for firemen and ambulance cars to access the bridge. The impact requirement is that invisible damage caused by impact may not grow up to a level of failure, during the life time of the bridge.

Another important difference between the two concepts is the transverse rigidity. The double layered concept with transverse road deck beams spreads the load better due to its higher transverse rigidity.

It was found that for this bridge, due to its small width, the limited transverse stiffness of the single deck structure is sufficient. Furthermore, the integrated deck concept means a large reduction in manufacturing and assembly costs.

Based on the cost evaluation, it was decided to continue with an integrated deck, according to concept IV, figure 3.

4 Design and details

The resulting structure consists of a single deck, integrating the road deck and span function into a single row of 16 beams. The beams are joined by means of adhesive and a cover laminate of 14mm, see figure 5. On top is a redundant layer that provides a safety buffer for smaller damages and for repair. The thickness varies from 5mm to 15mm to take care of the water flow of the bridge. On top there will be a thin layer of epoxy with wearing course, providing grip for the traffic and wear resistance for the structure. It is a glass fibre reinforced structure and both polyester resin as well as epoxy resin were considered.

Figure 5: overall bridge top view and cross section and section at the rotation point

The ends of the beams are closed separately by bonded end caps and connected by an integrally manufactured end wall, figure 6. The web distance of the beams is 200mm, and is determined by the width of the wheel print, because there is only a limited transverse spread of the load. The height of the beams is the maximum space available within the original foundation.

Figure 6: detail of the bonded end caps (side view)

Figure 7: material built up

4.1 Material built up and critical aspects

Figure 7 shows the material built up of the structure. The flanges of the beams are the girders of the structure and contain a large amount of uni-directional fibres. The coupling layers provide stiffness and strength in both directions, and mainly has a 0/90° orientation. The redundant layer is quasi-isotropic, as well as the webs. The webs are loaded in shear due to the bending and the vertical loads, but also on compression by the wheel loads. The built up is for this reason quasi-isotropic.

The integrated deck structure means that the strict impact and fire requirements must be fulfilled. Also, the load of the wheel print causes interlaminar shear stresses in the top layer. The most critical load case is the combination of a wheel print load and impact damage, for example caused by a truck losing a load.

To check the residual strength of the top layer, impact tests were performed on a reference specimen consisting of the top layer and approximately 50mm of webs (figure 8). Remarkable conclusion of the test is that the wearing course of the top surface of the bridge deck plays an important role in the dissipation of impact energy. As the grains crush at the contact with the impactor, it protects the underlying composite structure very effectively (figure 9).

Three delaminations

Figure 8: glass-polyester after ILS-fatigue Figure 9: glass-epoxy after impact: no damage

Figure 10: three point bending test set up

After impact, specimen were subjected to an inter laminar shear fatigue test. The specimen with glass fibre-polyester did not sustain this test: the damaged zone extended quickly under the load cycles of the traffic. The specimen with epoxy resin showed no damage growth.

Fire protection can be achieved in two ways:

- In the redundant layer a fire retarding resin is applied
- Application of an intumescent coating.

Important requirement is that the resin of the structure may not ignite and that sufficient structural strength is maintained for medical or fire brigades and repair of the structure.

A fire test was executed, in which the panel was placed in an oven for a duration of 30 min, with a maximum temperature of 800 °C. This test showed that this requirement is feasible, the penetration depth with fire retardant resin (Synolite 6815 N1, DSM) for the redundant layer and the cover laminate (20mm) was approximately 15mm, see figure 11.

Figure 11: panel after standard fire test exposition of 30 minutes. The upper 8.5mm of the glass-polyester specimen is carbonised.

4.2 Transverse rigidity of the integrated deck.

The integrated deck is analysed using Finite Element Methods to check the transverse load spreading of the concept and determine the deflection. From the result (figure 12) it is estimated that 80% of the beams contributes to the load carrying capacity. This confirms the applicability of the concept for this width and length.

Figure 12: deflection of the structure under a truck load of 450 kN.

The 'bath tub'-like deformation shows that the structure deforms as a panel. The transverse stiffness is achieved by the end walls of the structure, but also by bending of the webs, see figure 13. It was feared that in combination with a vertical wheel load, the deformed web would be sensitive to buckling. The occurring stresses and deformation were analyzed in a Finite Element evaluation and were found to be not critical for buckling or fatigue.

Figure 13: S-shape deformation of the web due to the transverse bending.

4.3 Connections

Four types of joints were applied in the design:

- Mechanical joints:
 - Fitted bolted joints
 - Axle joints
- Adhesive joints
- Laminated joints.

The many opening and closing cycles of the bridge impose fatigue loads on the joints of the hydraulic cylinder and hanging supports, but the main fatigue load is of course caused by the traffic. Fatigue is most critical in the dimensioning of the mechanical joints.

Figure 14: detail of the rotation point

Figure 15: the axle joint of the cylinder

Figure 14 shows the interface of the steel parts of the rotation point and the composite structure. This type of connection using fitted bolts was used at the rotation point and the locking mechanism. At the joint of both the cylinder as the hanging rods, a different type of load introduction was applied, see figure 15.

Design rules and safety factors for fatigue loads and long term environmental effect were applied to dimension and determine the strength of the joints. The joints are considered critical and a single lap test on ultimate strength and fatigue with large bolts in a thick laminate was performed as a proof of strength. The test set up for is seen in figure 16.

The beam to cover laminate laminated joint is also considered a primary load path. This joint was analysed using the analytical modelling of Volkersen, as well as FE-analysis. The theoretical analysis was verified by a test on ultimate strength figure 17.

Figure 16 : Test set up bolted joint

Figure 17: Test set up laminated and adhesive joint

Both joints sustained the tests successfully, with strength safety margins of 76% and 20% respectively. More details of the test can be found in [6].

5 Conclusion

An integrated deck concept as shown in figure 4 can be used for this type of bridge. A safe and reliable structure has been designed within all requirements of the Ministry of transport. The weight of the composite structural parts is 7780 kg. The structure is constructed out of simple elements and can be made cost effectively with a resin infusion technology. Critical aspects are the transverse stiffness, fatigue of the load introductions and the damage tolerance of the structure after impact. These items have been successfully demonstrated with analysis and tests.

6 References

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